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**Influence of Parenting Education on
Holistic Development of Public Preschool
Children in Abeokuta South Local
Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria**

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Abstract

This study explores the influence of parenting education on the holistic development of public preschool children in Abeokuta South Local Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria. The study investigates how parenting education programmes impact parental knowledge and skills related to child-rearing practices and how they consequently affect the holistic development of their children. The study adopted a descriptive survey research type, using random sampling to select a total of 70 parents and 30 child educators from 5 public preschools. Data were collected through structured questionnaires administered to parents and child educators in the selected public preschools, focusing on their experiences with parenting education and their perceptions of child development outcomes. The collected data were analysed using descriptive statistics. The findings revealed a high level of parenting education among the parents of preschoolers, and effective parenting education

programmes significantly enhance parents' confidence and competence in managing their children's developmental needs. Findings indicated that parental active participation, a stable environment, a curriculum that supports all areas of child development, child access to a balanced diet and nutrition, verbal communication skills, emotional support, and engagement in educational activities are predictors of holistic development. Furthermore, findings suggested expanding access and flexibility of parenting education programmes, ensuring that content is evidence-based and interactive, providing ongoing support for parents, and promoting community awareness about the importance of these initiatives.

Keywords: Parenting Education, Holistic Child Development, Preschool Children's Parents, Preschoolers

Introduction

The early years of a child's life are a critical period for growth, development, and learning. Early Childhood Education (ECE) is any group programme that is designed to promote children's intellectual, socio-emotional, language, and physical development (Olowe, Kutelu, and Majebi, 2014). Early childhood development dramatically influences a child's moral beliefs and character. A well-organized preschool centre that runs a developmentally appropriate programme is expected to ensure equal development of social, emotional, physical, and intellectual skills in every child (Alhosani, 2022). Early childhood development must be holistic, encompassing social, emotional, physical, and cognitive domains. According to Britto et al (2017), ECE is generally aimed at promoting the holistic development of children from birth to age 8. It forms the social, emotional, physical, and cognitive foundations of every child.

Holistic child development is a multi-layered approach that nurtures and helps early childhood learners thrive in every aspect of their lives. This approach does not solely focus on one area but rather emphasizes the overall growth and development of the child. This comprehensive approach views the child as a whole person and guides their development in all areas, including physical, mental, emotional, social, and spiritual realms. A holistic approach recognizes that these domains are interconnected; for example, a child's emotional well-being can affect their ability to learn and interact with peers. Additionally, holistic education seeks to incorporate principles of wholeness, interconnectedness, and spirituality with the help of all the stakeholders that surround the child, especially the parents.

Parents are the primary caregivers and first teachers of their children. Parents play a crucial role in the lives of their children from the early years of life, as the early years of life are critical and sensitive periods when children's optimal development is most critical for laying the groundwork for lifelong learning. A veteran teacher (Downey, 2015) shared her reflection based on her experience that when parents are aware, encouraging, and involved, children do better and thereby enhance holistic development. Child educators alone cannot effectively educate children if parents do not prioritize education and provide support in the home. Parents must prioritize their roles and responsibilities in the holistic development of their children to assist teachers in their quest to provide quality holistic development to children.

Parenting in the early years requires parents to offer both care and learning opportunities for their children. The child's first relationships are critical for the establishment of competences- cognitive, social-emotional, and self-regulatory skills and as such, set the stage for lifelong adaptation and functioning. Parental education and quality support are crucial for the holistic development of children and their academic success (Shahidullah, 2019). Parenting education encompasses various practices that equip parents with the knowledge and skills needed to foster their children's development effectively (Agupusi, 2019).

Parental education significantly impacts the way parents interact and educate their children. Salami (2015) suggested that parents need to understand how their involvement and educational background can influence the developmental outcomes of their children. However, there is still a scarcity of research on the relationship between parental education and holistic childhood education in Abeokuta South Local Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria. The purpose of this study was to investigate the parental education and holistic child development in Abeokuta. The novelty of this study lies in the object of research, parenting education, and ways in which parenting education programmes can help in shaping children's cognitive, language, physical, and social-emotional development in the early years of life.

Statement of the Problem

The holistic development of preschool children is critically influenced by the quality and effectiveness of parenting education. In Abeokuta South Local

Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria, there is a growing concern regarding the adequacy of parenting education and its impact on holistic development outcomes. Despite the recognized importance of early childhood education, several issues such as inadequate funding, limited resources and services, socioeconomic factors, and insufficiently trained professionals could hinder appropriate child holistic development outcomes. This may lead to developmental delays, poor academic achievement/performance, and behavioural problems among preschool children. Given these challenges, it is essential to examine the current state of parenting education and its relationship with the holistic development of preschool children in Abeokuta South Local Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria. This study aims to identify existing gaps in parenting practices, explore the socio-cultural factors impacting them, and provide insights that can inform local interventions and policies. By addressing these issues, the study seeks to promote a supportive framework for parents, ultimately benefiting the developmental outcomes of preschool children in the study area.

Objectives of the Study

The main aim of this study is to assess parenting education and holistic development among preschool children's parents in the Abeokuta South Local Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria. The objectives are to:

- i. Ascertain the current level of parenting education among preschool parents in Abeokuta South Local Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria;
- ii. Identify the predictors of holistic development outcomes among preschool children in Abeokuta South Local Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following questions were answered in the study:

1. What is the current level of parenting education among parents of preschoolers in Abeokuta South Local Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria?
2. What are the predictors of holistic development outcomes among preschool children in Abeokuta South Local Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria?

Literature Review

Parenting education plays a foundational role in shaping the developmental trajectories of preschool children. Assessing the current level of parenting education among preschoolers' parents reveals significant variability based on context, resources, and programme availability. A study by Sunarsih et al. (2023) demonstrated that while only 58.33% of parents initially had a good understanding of holistic parenting, targeted education interventions increased this to 100%, suggesting substantial knowledge gaps that can be addressed through structured programmes (Sunarsih et al., 2023). Similarly, in a large-scale study from China, parental engagement was found to vary widely, yet it was significantly associated with improved developmental outcomes in cognitive, social, and emotional domains (Yang & Tahir, 2023).

Parental involvement stands out as a consistent and powerful determinant. Yang and Tahir (2023) found strong correlations between parental engagement and children's development in communication, early math, and socioemotional skills. These findings were supported by Widaningsih (2023), who emphasized that parenting patterns integrated into early childhood curricula, especially peer parenting, enhanced not only academic but also emotional and social domains of development (Widaningsih, 2023). Moreover, studies from Hong Kong indicated that congruence between parental perceptions and the goals of holistic education promotes environments that support comprehensive child development (Ng et al., 2020).

The extent to which parenting education directly predicts holistic development outcomes has also been well documented. Latifah and Hernawati (2009) showed that children enrolled in character-based holistic education programmes, often driven by strong parental involvement, displayed significantly higher levels of multiple intelligences than those in traditional or no preschool settings (Latifah & Hernawati, 2009). This was echoed in Sunarsih et al.'s (2023) research, which illustrated how holistic parenting, complemented by nutritional and health care practices, substantially improved cognitive and physical development. Furthermore, Widaningsih (2023) underscored that when parenting approaches are aligned with school-based curricula and supported by educators, the developmental outcomes are amplified across intellectual, emotional, and social domains.

Developing effective, evidence-based parenting education programmes requires a multifaceted approach. One of the most promising strategies is the integration of parenting education into the formal preschool curriculum. As Widaningsih (2023) found, this integration facilitates seamless collaboration between teachers and parents, allowing for the shared promotion of children's potential. Additionally, nature-based and experiential learning methods have proven effective in engaging parents and children alike, with Ripeanu (2024) showing how using natural materials in learning can support social-emotional and cognitive development (Ripeanu, 2024). Community-embedded models also stand out as essential: Ambari Sumanto et al. (2021) illustrated how involving parents in the planning and execution of nutrition and wellness programmes at preschools significantly boosted developmental outcomes (Ambari Sumanto et al., 2021). Training and support for teachers in engaging parents, as shown by Zeltserman et al. (2018), further enhance the impact of these initiatives (Zeltserman et al., 2018).

Theoretical Framework

Lev Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory, first articulated in the early 1930s, emphasises that children develop cognitively and socially through guided interactions within their cultural and social environments (Vygotsky, 1978). At its core is the concept of the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), the gap between what a child can do independently and what they can achieve with appropriate guidance and support. In the context of parenting education, this theory suggests that parents serve as primary agents of development by providing "scaffolding", temporary, structured support that enables children to achieve developmental milestones they could not reach on their own. Parenting education grounded in sociocultural theory thus trains parents to actively engage in such interactions, equipping them to foster children's cognitive, emotional, and language development through sensitive and responsive communication (Zhou, 2024; Edwards, 2009). This approach is particularly effective in early childhood education settings where the family is recognised as a co-contributor to learning and development (Selzing-Musa, 2014).

When applied to public preschool settings, parenting education informed by sociocultural principles supports holistic development by enhancing five interrelated domains. First, cognitive development is promoted as parents'

guide children through tasks requiring problem-solving, attention, and memory, core elements shaped by joint activity in the ZPD (Zhou, 2024). Second, language development is advanced through dialogic interactions that serve as both cognitive tools and pathways to social understanding. Third, socio-emotional development benefits from parental modelling of empathy, emotional regulation, and relationship-building. Fourth, physical development, though less emphasised by Vygotsky, is influenced by culturally mediated practices like play and fine-motor tasks facilitated by parental engagement. Finally, cultural responsiveness is fostered as parents transmit values, traditions, and social norms, embedding the child's development in a culturally meaningful context (Edwards, 2007; Zhou, 2024). Together, these domains reflect how sociocultural theory provides a practical and theoretical foundation for designing parenting education programmes that support preschool children's full developmental potential in public educational systems.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research type. The target population for this study consisted of all parents and preschool teachers in Abeokuta South Local Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria. Random sampling was used to select a total of 70 parents and 30 preschool teachers from 5 public preschools in Abeokuta South Local Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria. Two research instruments, tagged "Parenting Education Questionnaire (PEQ) and Holistic Child Development Questionnaire (HCDQ)", were used to gather information for the study. Parenting Education Questionnaire (PEQ) was used to assess parents' knowledge, skills, and practices relating to parenting education, while Holistic Child Development Questionnaire (HCDQ) was used to assess children's holistic development outcomes (cognitive, language or linguistic, physical, and social-emotional). The data collected was analysed using descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) while the hypothesis was tested using Pearson Product product-moment correlation at the 0.05 level of significance.

Results and Discussion

Research Question One: What is the current level of parenting education (knowledge, skills, and practice) among parents of preschoolers in Abeokuta South Local Government Area? Ogun State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Descriptive level of parenting education (knowledge, skills, and practice) among parents of preschoolers

	Items	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	Std.D
1	I engage in activities that promote my child's physical development (e.g., outdoor play, sports).	68 (68%)	23 (23%)	6 (6%)	3 (3%)	3.56	0.953
2	I regularly read to my child to enhance their language skills.	54 (54%)	21 (21%)	15 (15%)	10 (10%)	3.19	.832
3	I provide opportunities for my child to interact with peers.	34 (34%)	18 (18%)	34 (34%)	14 (14%)	2.72	.753
4	I encourage my child to express their emotions and feelings.	67 (67%)	17 (17%)	12 (12%)	4 (4%)	3.47	.672
5	I feel confident in my ability to support my child's learning and development	31 (31%)	43 (43%)	16 (16%)	10 (10%)	2.95	.962
6	I have learned skills to manage my child's behaviour effectively	23 (23%)	17 (17%)	38 (38%)	22 (22%)	2.41	1.021
7	I know how to implement routines	48 (48%)	26 (26%)	18 (18%)	8 (8%)	3.14	.673

	that promote my child's well-being.						
8	I can effectively communicate with my child to foster a safe environment	36 (36%)	29 (29%)	24 (24%)	11 (11%)	2.90	.849
9	I understand the key milestones of physical development in a child	40 (40%)	35 (35%)	18 (18%)	7 (7%)	3.08	.964
10	I am knowledgeable about the importance of social skills in early childhood.	37 (37%)	36 (36%)	21 (21%)	6 (6%)	3.04	.780
11	I am aware of strategies to enhance my child's emotional intelligence.	22 (22%)	30 (30%)	19 (19%)	29 (29%)	2.45	1.010
<i>Decision at mean score greater than 2.5 or less than. Weighted Mean = 3.291</i>							

Table 1 above shows the levels of parenting education (knowledge, skills, and practice) among parents of preschoolers. From the table, it was observed that the majority (91%) of the respondents indicated that they engage in activities that promote children's physical development (e.g., outdoor play, sports), with $\bar{x} = 3.56$. Also, 75% strongly agreed that they do regularly read to their children to enhance their language skills having mean value of 3.19, while 52% indicated that they do provide opportunities for their children to interact with peers having mean value of 2.71. In the same vein, it was observed that 84% of the parents encouraged children to express their emotions and feelings, with a mean value of 3.47. In addition, 74% of the parents feel confident in their ability to support their child's learning and development, and 72% indicated that they know how to implement routines

that promote the children's wellbeing, with a mean of 2.95 and 3.14, respectively.

Furthermore, 65% of the respondents strongly agreed that they can effectively communicate with their children to foster a safe environment, while 35% of respondents had a contrary view of the statements. I understand the key milestones of physical development in children, as 75% of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement. In the same vein, 83% of the respondents strongly agreed that they are knowledgeable about the importance of social skills in early childhood. This means that the majority of the parents have high knowledge, skills, and practices that can enhance children's holistic development. Based on the weighted mean value of $\bar{x} = 3.291$, which is above the criterion mean value of $\bar{x} = 2.50$, it can be inferred that there is a high level of parenting education among the parents of the preschoolers. This implies that the parents of the preschoolers possess a high level of knowledge, skills, and practices of holistic child development.

Research Question 2: What are the predictors of holistic child development outcomes among preschool children in Abeokuta South Local Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Descriptive predictors of holistic child development outcomes among preschoolers

Items	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	Std.D
1 Parents' active participation in their child's preschool activities enhances holistic development.	44 (44%)	29 (29%)	17 (17%)	10 (10%)	3.07	.705
2 There is adequate provision of a stable environment for my child's development	37 (37%)	42 (42%)	12 (12%)	9 (9%)	3.07	.815
3 The curriculum supports all areas of child development (cognitive, social,	28 (28%)	33 (33%)	27 (27%)	12 (12%)	2.77	.945

	emotional, and physical).						
4	Teachers have appropriate qualifications and training for early childhood education.	18 (18%)	28 (28%)	36 (36%)	18 (18%)	2.46	1.052
5	There is a good teacher-to-child ratio, allowing for personalized interactions among preschoolers	22 (22%)	15 (15%)	27 (27%)	36 (36%)	2.23	1.201
6	My child has access to a balanced diet and nutrition.	34 (34%)	27 (27%)	23 (23%)	16 (16%)	2.79	.824
7	My child demonstrates strong verbal communication skills for their age.	39 (39%)	25 (25%)	24 (24%)	12 (12%)	2.91	.739
8	The preschool provides support for children's social-emotional and mental well-being.	45 (45%)	18 (18%)	23 (23%)	14 (14%)	2.94	.659
<i>Decision at mean score greater than 2.5 or less than. Weighted Mean = 2.78</i>							

Table 2 reveals the predictors of holistic child development outcomes among preschoolers in selected preschools. From the Table, respondents strongly indicated that parents' active participation in their child's preschool activities enhances holistic development, with a mean value of 3.07. Also, the majority (79%) strongly agreed that adequate provision of a stable environment for children enhances children's development, with a mean value of 3.07. Moreover, participants believed that the curriculum effectively fosters all aspects of child development (cognitive, social, emotional, and physical), which are strong indicators of comprehensive

outcomes in child development. The result from the table revealed that children have access to a balanced diet and nutrition, and equally demonstrate strong verbal communication skills for their age, and preschools that provide support for children's emotional and mental well-being are further indicated as a good predictor of children's holistic development. Though the number of appropriate teachers trained in early childhood education qualification and the teacher-to-child ratio to allow for personalized interactions among preschools were observed as predictors of holistic child development, rated with a mean value below the criterion mean. The general observation shows that parental active participation, stable environment and home support, curriculum that supports all areas of child development (cognitive, social, emotional, and physical), child access to a balanced diet and nutrition, verbal communication skills and preschool provides support for children's emotional and mental well-being, professional teacher qualification and teacher-to-child ratio are predictors holistic development among preschoolers.

Discussion

The results of the present study reveal that preschool children's parents have a strong understanding, skills, and practices related to holistic child development. This agrees with Ng et al view (2020) that parents in Hong Kong aligned well with holistic education goals, showing informed practices. However, Sunarsih et al. (2023) reported that only 58.33% of parents initially demonstrated adequate knowledge, which improved significantly after parenting education. This suggests that while some parents are well-informed, others require structured support to build essential skills.

As for the key predictors of holistic development in pre-schoolers, the results show that active parental involvement, a stable environment, home support, a curriculum covering all areas of child development (cognitive, social, emotional, and physical), access to a balanced diet and nutrition, verbal communication skills, and preschool support for emotional and mental well-being - along with qualified teachers and an appropriate teacher-to-child ratio influences the holistic development in pre-schoolers. Research has shown strong links between parental engagement and children's cognitive, emotional, and social growth (Yang and Tahir, 2023). Latifah and Hernawati (2009), on the other hand, show that holistic programmes with qualified teachers improved multiple intelligences. However, Sunarsih et al.

(2023) noted that without structured support, key predictors like nutrition and home practices may be inconsistently applied, limiting their overall impact.

Conclusion

The assessment of parenting education and its impact on the holistic development of preschool children in Abeokuta South Local Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria, underscores the critical role that informed and engaged parenting involvement in child development. The findings indicated that effective parenting education programmes can significantly improve parents' knowledge and skills regarding child-rearing practices, leading to enhanced developmental outcomes for preschoolers. Parents who participated in evidence-based programmes reported greater confidence in their parenting abilities, better communication with their children, and an increased ability to meet their children's emotional, social, cognitive, and physical needs. Investing in quality parenting education is paramount for fostering holistic development in preschool children. Despite the positive outcomes observed, challenges such as limited access to programmes, varying levels of parental engagement, and disparities in socio-economic status are noted. These factors can influence the effectiveness of parenting education initiatives. Thus, it is essential to address these barriers to maximise the potential benefits of these programmes. By improving access, enhancing programme content, and strengthening support systems, the preschools in the study can create a supportive environment where children thrive and reach their full potential.

Recommendations

Based on the assessment findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Government, preschools and child education providers should increase the availability and accessibility of parenting education programmes across diverse community settings, ensuring that all parents, regardless of socioeconomic status, can participate.
2. All stakeholders in early childhood education should ensure that the content of parenting education programmes incorporates interactive and practical learning experiences, such as workshops and group

- discussions, to engage parents actively and to facilitate skills application.
3. Governments and preschool administrators should provide continuous support and resources to parents after they complete parenting education programmes. This can include follow-up meetings, support groups, and access to educational materials.
 4. Government and preschool stakeholders should implement campaigns to educate parents about the importance of holistic child development and the benefits of parenting education.
 5. Community events and activities that promote parent-child interactions and facilitate the sharing of parenting experiences among families should be encouraged in Abeokuta South Local Government Area, other parts of Ogun State, and Nigeria at large.
 6. Parents should spend quality time with their children, engaging them in activities that will help them grow into well-rounded individuals.

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